

IPERION HS

CALL: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1

GA n. 871034

D.6.2 Exploitation Plan

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Document information

Project number	871034	Acronym	IPERION HS
Full title	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science		
Project url	www.iperionhs.eu		
EU Project Officer	Simona Misiti		

Deliverable	Number	D.6.2	Title	Exploitation Plan
Work Package	Number	6	Title	Innovation and Exploitation

Deliverable nature	<input type="checkbox"/> prototype <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> report <input type="checkbox"/> demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> other		
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted		
Contractual delivery date	(30/09/2021)		
Actual delivery date	(31/12/2021)		
Status	Version 2c	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final	

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Total number of pages	18
Keywords	Innovation, exploitation, sustainability, heritage science

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
06/12/2021	-	D. Anglos	original
10/12/2021	1	All co-authors	revisions
28/01/2022	2	D. Anglos	final

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Abstract

This document outlines aspects of innovation considered relevant for HS and proposes general actions for an Exploitation plan.

Innovation is an essential component of the strategic objectives of E-RIHS. It encompasses novel research actions, offer of unique access services and provision of smart tools. Exploiting innovation, for the benefit of the E-RIHS ecosystem and the society, requires a number of actions along the innovation chain, including the presence of an efficient monitoring and evaluation system, appropriate knowledge and technology transfer channels, proper IPR protection and efficient communication with key stakeholders both in the public and the private sectors. An overall systematic approach to the above will ensure success and sustainability of E-RIHS as an innovator and as a leader in the global HS landscape.

This document is Deliverable 6.2, elaborated in the context of project IPERION HS, WP-06: *Innovation and Exploitation*, Task 6.4: *Exploitation Plan*. The analysis for the work presented herein was based on extensive interactions between the co-authors and builds upon a number of documents produced in the context of IPERION HS and E-RIHS PP (in particular Deliverable 9.4: *Innovation Agenda*).

Table of contents

Document information	2
Abstract	3
Table of contents	4
Abbreviations	6
Narrative (technical) description	7
1. <i>Introduction</i>	7
2. <i>E-RIHS as an Innovation Ecosystem</i>	7
3. <i>What is it there to exploit and how can this be done?</i>	10
4. <i>Actions towards exploitation</i>	11
Mapping of key achievements across IPERION HS.....	11
Identifying research and application areas that require further development	11
Engaging the User Communities.....	13
Monitoring Innovation	13
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)	14
5. <i>Exploitation Plan. Objectives.</i>	15
Training of researchers.....	15
Central Liaison Office (CLO) for Innovation	16
Facilitating exploitation – Lowering barriers	16
Innovation radar	16
Collaboration with Industry.....	16
6. <i>Concluding remarks</i>	17
Useful references	18

List of figures and tables

Figure 1: E-RIHS PP Innovation Survey results on most common areas where innovations are made

Figure 2: Snapshots of the IPERION HS catalogue of services

Figure 3: Numerical KPIs per Set Objective

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CHARISMA	Cultural heritage Advanced Research Infrastructures: Synergy for a Multidisciplinary Approach to Conservation/Restoration
CLARIN	The research infrastructure for language as social and cultural data
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
E-RIHS PP	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science – Preparatory Phase
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures
ESS	European Social Survey
EU	European Union
EU-Artech	Access, research and technology for the conservation of the European cultural heritage
HS	Heritage Science
ICCROM	International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property
IPERION CH	Access, research and technology for the conservation of the European cultural heritage
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
JRA	Joint Research Activity
Labs-Tech	Laboratories on Science and Technology for the conservation of the European Cultural Heritage
TNA	Trans National Access
WP	Work Package

Narrative (technical) description

1. Introduction

The IPERION HS, “Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science”, project (GA 871034) integrates a range of national facilities, recognized for their expertise in the field of Heritage Science (HS), to create an open infrastructure of institutions and specialist researchers, engaged in collaborative research and providing advanced services across the wider field of Heritage Science.

In the context of WP6, Innovation and Exploitation, IPERION HS, as an advanced community, aims at maximizing its socio-economic innovation potential to serve Heritage Science and the society. Project developments will find exploitation routes in the future E-RIHS (European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science), specifically through improved interoperability of instruments and digital documentation. This will reinforce the long-term sustainability of the distributed RI and increase its impact on the European Research Area (ERA).

Specific objectives of WP6 are:

- To formulate an innovation strategy to impact industry and promote its clustering with the RI in focus, promoting their involvement beyond technology development, thus opening the possibilities for future public-private partnerships.
- To promote sustainability of the RI by developing a partnership strategy for smart future innovation based on identification of excellence and specialization across Europe and by identifying a framework of sustainable collaboration to promote the presence of cultural heritage in the national agendas for research and innovation.
- To improve the interoperability by investigating and comparing protocols, instrument parameters and practices for documenting data, and by defining the project Data Management Plan.
- To exploit all aspects of innovation achieved within IPERION HS and its preceding projects in the future E-RIHS by mapping key achievements and diverse expertise across the partnership, identifying research and application areas that require further development and by engaging the user community in the enhancement of access services.
- To implementing a strategy for management of IPR issues.

This document provides an overview along with an initial set of general guidelines concerning exploitation of innovative results in IPERION HS and more broadly in E-RIHS.

2. E-RIHS as an Innovation Ecosystem

Over the past nearly 20 years, a sequence of integrating activities, LabS-TECH (FP5), EU-ARTECH (FP6), CHARISMA (FP7), IPERION CH (H2020) and now IPERION HS have defined and consolidated a strong baseline that has led to the development of the concept of E-RIHS.

E-RIHS constitutes a platform for interdisciplinary partnership with the aim to address major scientific and technical challenges in HS, often beyond the realm of pure science and technology. It allows access to state-of-the-art equipment and facilities, top-level expertise, data, archives and collections, in an innovative way. E-RIHS is open to collaboration with other RIs seeking to exchange best practices and take advantage of innovations deriving from other scientific fields: Furthermore, E-RIHS encourages and facilitates innovation

through different types of collaboration and strategic partnerships (e.g. among providers, between providers and users, with industry, at global, EU or regional levels). A major ambition of E-RIHS is to promote a culture of innovation all across the spectrum of its research activities, in the access services provided, through its unique training activities and even at the management level, exploring new models for maximising the impact of HS research on scientific knowledge, technological know-how and socio-economic growth based on the sustainable use of cultural heritage.

An innovative concept in itself, E-RIHS offers access to large-scale and medium-scale analytical facilities (FIXLAB), to an impressive array of advanced mobile analytical instrumentation (MOLAB), as well as to invaluable scientific datasets archived in knowledge repositories of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions (ARCHLAB). In addition, it combines these services with unique expertise in designing or optimising sophisticated scientific investigations and proper approaches for analysis and interpretation, specific to the targeted object or material, revealing their complex microstructure and chemical composition, giving essential and invaluable insights into historical technologies, materials, alteration and degradation phenomena or authenticity. E-RIHS aims at growing opportunities for innovation by exploiting the prolific interaction and collaboration between providers and users through the provided TNA services, building also strong links with industrial partners and the broader heritage industry.

E-RIHS: Innovation in Research, Training and Outreach

The MOLAB concept, introduced in 2003, was a highly innovative approach satisfying the needs of heritage researchers, who needed to make use of advanced diagnostic methods but were not in a position to move objects and not allowed to collect samples.

Now, IPERION HS offers MOLAB TNA with over 20 mobile instruments developed over the years.

Image © IPERION CH MOLAB Project

Through collaborative work in the IPERION CH project (WP6, JRA1: Innovative instruments and methods for integrated approaches to CH analysis and diagnostics), researchers at AGLAE, together with colleagues at BNC, IPANEMA and SOLEIL developed a versatile 3D positioner which enables accurate and reliable elemental mapping of non-flat surfaces of heritage objects.

T. Calligaro et al. "A new 3D positioner for the analytical mapping of non-flat objects under accelerator beams". *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B*: 467 (2020), pp. 65–72.

3rd IPERION-CH Doctoral Summer School, 16–20 July 2018, University of Bologna – Ravenna Campus (Italy).

The E-RIHS community has established a series of Doctoral Summer Schools, which are addressed to young PhD and post-doctoral researchers, the future users of E-RIHS facilities.

The 1st HS Academy Doctoral Summer School, in the IPERION HS project, was held virtually (13-16.07.2021) attracting 190 attendees from all around the world.

IPERION HS and E-RIHS have initiated a series of monthly webinars, which constitute a key source of state-of-the-art information on HS research, facilities, policy and impact. The series contributes to the development of a vibrant HS community and is intended for anyone involved in interdisciplinary heritage research.

Significant innovations developed so far in the E-RIHS organizations have emerged over the past decade through a number of projects supported by the EC, including those related to RIs, as well as relevant national initiatives. Most of these innovations (see E-RIHS-PP, D9.2 and also Fig. 1) may be classified as follows:

- **Research-based:** novel analytical tools based on emerging technologies and cutting-edge engineering that allow to efficiently address or improve the characterization of heritage materials or structures
- **Heritage (Use)-led:** new methodologies that enable a global, multi-parameter understanding of heritage objects
- **Access type:** novel and efficient modes of access to analytical technologies (FIXLAB, MOLAB), physical archives (ARCHLAB) or online scientific data (DIGILAB) that increase opportunities for exchange, interaction and close cooperation among a broad spectrum of providers and user communities on a truly interdisciplinary basis
- **Knowledge spillover-technology transfer** (primarily inward): adaptation of tools and methods from other fields and disciplines such as geosciences (GIS), biology and medicine (genetic methods, imaging), materials science and nanotechnology (new materials for conservation); mathematics and computer science (data handling and processing and data management)
- **Access policy:** open data sharing and e-infrastructures that ensure sustainable, open digital archives through the development of research e-infrastructure computing facilities and e-services, cloud based services, data mining or other HS relevant services.

Figure 1: E-RIHS PP Innovation Survey results on most common areas where innovations are made

A profound point of strength of E-RIHS is the catalogue of TNA services, currently implemented in the context of IPERION HS, which encompasses a rich and broad variety of cutting-edge tools dedicated to provide unique services to diverse user communities. These tools include: Instruments and workstations; Techniques and methodologies; Integrated multi-technique methods; Interdisciplinary approaches for data processing and interpretation.

Given the current experience, many more innovations can be developed through E-RIHS in additional areas producing, for example, non-economic, non-technological and social innovations. It is noted that the overall environment is favourable. At the present stage a number of key RIs, aspiring to serve various heritage research communities are developing under the umbrella of ESFRI, including pan-European RIs in the SSH domain (DARIAH, CLARIN, ESS, SHARE and CESSDA), and E-RIHS.

Beyond the direct impacts related to increasing the quality and efficiency of scientific output in HS, E-RIHS activities are expected to provide further impacts benefitting the scientific community, sector operators and the public at large. Thus, Europeans, more broadly, and public services more specifically, will benefit from better access to non-technical knowledge, improved awareness and increased understanding of artistic and cultural assets. Finally, implementing various types of innovations in heritage institutions can enhance the

access of citizens to culture, strengthen its message to society and generate positive impact on cultural tourism.

Further, with respect to the context of the HS-society interactions, as pointed out in the interim report on Innovation Strategy (WP6, Task 6.1¹) new challenges might arise in relation to human wellbeing and mental health domains. Studies have shown that access to heritage sites can improve people's mental health and wellbeing and admittedly this has been especially brought to light during lockdowns and travel restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic. A rather small but active community of researchers has been working in areas of psychiatry and psychology, however interactions between them and mainstream Heritage Science are negligible if not zero. A new opportunity for E-RIHS might be to engage with scientists working in mental health and wellbeing, perhaps as part of a potential new user community.

3. What is it there to exploit and how can this be done?

It is understood that different sorts of innovations emerge in the E-RIHS ecosystem, demonstrating a strong potential for exploitation. Yet it is commonly admitted that innovation examples, successfully exploited by E-RIHS partners, are disproportionately few in comparison to its innovation potential. This has been a major finding of the Innovation Survey carried out in the context of E-RIHS PP and presented in D9.2². Likewise, the Interim Report on Innovation Strategy of the IPERION HS project (WP6, Task 6.1) identifies fragmentation and the lack of efficient mechanisms as a major obstacle to the path for exploiting innovation in a constructive manner. These findings suggest that there exist gaps that prevent exploitation and commercialization of innovation produced in the context of HS facilities.

Taking a step back, a number of questions can be asked at this stage that need to be addressed:

- What is it worth exploiting? [Definition of 'exploitable product', Identification of product potential]
- In what ways could an innovative instrument/method/approach be exploited? [Exploitation plan and methodology]
- Which is the potential '(heritage) market place' and how strong its interest? [Identify markets and interest]
- Which would be the expected benefits? What would be their value? [Value chain and profit]
- Who could/should undertake the effort of exploitation? [Resources and key partnership(s), Facilitators, Training needs]
- What are potential obstacles and inhibitors?

Some of these questions may be answered by E-RIHS providers, others require involvement of experts with the appropriate professional background, commonly members of Technology Transfer Offices (TTO). Interaction between researchers on the one hand (technology/services providers or users) and TT experts on the other, is expected to facilitate the transfer of innovative achievements to the Heritage Marketplace.

Innovations deriving from E-RIHS could be exploited using four common pathways: Licensing agreements; Establishing new companies; Creating joint ventures; Outright sale of innovations. However, the most suitable way of exploitation will depend upon several factors (e.g. IP rights, market size, resources needed, etc.). Technology transfer (TT) and exploitation experts will specifically advise the involved parties on the

¹ A. Gibson, WP6-MS7 "Interim report on Innovation Strategy".

² E-RIHS PP Deliverable D9.2 "Analysis of the Innovation Background".

optimal exploitation route and various possibilities taking into consideration the unique characteristics and feature of each individual case that needs to be further exploited. The final decisions about the exploitation route will have to be made by the involved parties and their organisations.

Next, a set of general actions are proposed that offer an approach to dealing with the questions/concerns outlined above.

4. Actions towards exploitation

Mapping of key achievements across IPERION HS

Already evident, via a look at the IPERION HS catalogue of services, major achievements lie on instrumentation and technologies, measurement methodologies and protocols, as well as documentation tools and data management procedures. A sample of these services is given in two snapshots from the IPERION HS website (Fig. 2).

A more detailed account on the type of innovation cases achieved, as seen by members of the E-RIHS Infrastructures (and a few more representatives of other RIs active in HS), has been provided by the outcome of the Innovation Survey conducted in the context of the E-RIHS PP project and can be found in the corresponding deliverable, D9.2. Based on this Survey, innovations in E-RIHS were classified in four (4) main types:

- New/adapted instrumentation
- New methodologies
- Knowledge transfer
- User facilitation/new services / Data support and recording

An important aspect to take into consideration is that most of these innovations are continuously assessed and evolving, particularly when they are put into practice, and a critical factor for this progress is the involvement of users (co-creation). But furthermore, this continuous evolution requires the presence of a mechanism and indicators appropriate for monitoring and evaluating the potential of existing or new ideas and tools, identifying emerging opportunities for innovation.

Identifying research and application areas that require further development

As outlined in the E-RIHS Scientific Strategy³. (E-RIHS PP D9.3), the E-RIHS infrastructure will specifically address research on **tangible heritage**, keeping in mind that the understanding and “preservation of cultural heritage link materials and their physical condition (tangible) to their cultural significance and meaning (intangible)”.

Heritage Science projects raise crucial questions related to cultural and natural heritage materials. Many of these questions are intrinsically complex. They have their origin in the humanities, but require the use of advanced scientific techniques, engaging researchers from different disciplines in collaborative work. This has a distinct impact on the entire research process, requiring that the object of study is placed at the heart of the research rationale. The main science drivers aim at:

³ E-RIHS PP Deliverable 9.3 “Scientific Strategy”

Figure 2: Snapshots of the IPERION HS catalogue of services⁴

Enhancing Knowledge of Heritage: Improving knowledge of heritage systems involves understanding their origin and technical context, evolution and history, circulation and use, as well as the political, cultural or symbolic values they embody.

Preserving Heritage: The study of the deterioration of heritage objects over time, the diagnosis of their current state and the development of means to ensure their conservation and restoration is a necessary undertaking to enable their transmission to future generations.

Developing New Capabilities for Heritage Science: Serving as a model RI aims at providing creative tools and new ways of generating scientific information and knowledge and developing long-term partnerships that are expected to play a key role in building long-term research capacity in the community beyond the existing

⁴ <https://www.iperionhs.eu/catalogue-of-services/>

fragmentation. Novel instruments, workstations and techniques emerge continuously as a result of technological innovations and enable scientists to address challenging analytical problems. But often the diffusion of novel tools to other research communities, for instance in the field of HS, is often slow despite the fact that relevant technical and methodological adaptations demonstrate that such tools enable alternative, often improved, capabilities concerning the compositional characterization of materials and objects. Getting through such bottlenecks and making top-level instrumentation accessible to user communities requires scientists (and engineers) in access providing facilities to work together with potential users in order to identify those innovative areas of application where the use of such a new tool will provide distinct advantages.

Engaging the User Communities

Of particular significance for E-RIHS, as an innovation ecosystem, is that users can no longer be considered as an inanimate part of the whole research process. They play an active role and their expertise should be nurtured for idea generation to diffusion stages in the innovation chain.

In a multi-disciplinary RI such as E-RIHS, significant potential for innovation can lie with the users evolving into providers. Becoming a provider to a co-creation ecosystem means, that not only the need but also the critical capacity exists to justify it. In the case of E-RIHS, for instance, users of MOLAB may create or refine portable equipment for applying a specific technique to a particular type of object. This idea may have been generated from unfulfilled needs in existing MOLAB facilities. An innovation ecosystem such as E-RIHS is a suitable environment where such unfulfilled needs translate into research areas.

To address some of these points a few questions have been included in the questionnaire (QUESTIONNAIRE ON RESEARCH INTEREST/NEEDS IN THE FIELD OF HERITAGE SCIENCE) distributed through National Coordinators to users of National RIs based in the different member states. These questions aim to evaluate how users perceive the quality and impact of access and to identify potential needs for enhancing access services.

Specific use cases will be examined based on selected TNA projects carried out in the first 28 months of IPERION HS in the ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB platforms. Main objective will be to see how knowledge generated through access to advanced platforms is exploited in order to create impact both academic and non-academic.

Monitoring Innovation

The ability to move effectively and constructively from innovation to exploitation, requires the establishment of appropriate non-intrusive and straightforward mechanisms capable to monitor the generation and growth of innovation from its early stages.

The role of E-RIHS in innovation is to foster generation of ideas and monitor the conversion and diffusion stages. In order to properly monitor innovation derived from E-RIHS it is essential to set up an internal mechanism that will liaise with local technology transfer units (if they are in place) at the participating organizations that are in charge of assessing the innovation produced, in an effort to exchange good practices and optimize actions at the local level and overall. Furthermore, certain procedures and methodologies should be introduced for monitoring all steps along the innovation pipeline. An **evaluation mechanism** needs to be established to **monitor progress, advice on key areas for development, indicate exploitation opportunities** and **suggest adjustments** when things go wrong. In the same context, a **central online registry** should be created that will record certain KPIs and keep track of the research and innovation actions performed within E-RIHS.

A systematic approach in defining metrics and indicators (KPIs) that would provide a reliable assessment of the innovation impact is essential. This is expected to maximize the visibility of E-RIHS and contribute to enhancing the E-RIHS potential for attracting investments and producing further innovations with impact in various fields and researcher communities. E-RIHS is in complete alliance with the recent suggestion of the ESFRI working group as recorded in the “*Monitoring of Research Infrastructures Performance*” report.⁵ Therefore, E-RIHS is adopting the KPIs suggested by the ESFRI working group for monitoring purposes (Figure 3). Aligned with the ESFRI KPIs model, and per set objective, certain additional KPIs or adapted to HS domain specificities need to be set and measured in order to monitor more specifically performance vs innovation, for example, as regards TNA modalities and implementation, training activities, dissemination activities etc.⁶.

Objective	KPIs
Enabling scientific excellence	1. Number of user requests for access 2. Number of users served 3. Number of publications 4. Percentage of top (10%) cited publications
Delivery of education and training	5. Number of master and PhD students using the RI 6. Training of people who are not RI staff
Enhancing collaboration in Europe	7. Number of members of the RI from ESFRI countries 8. Share of users and publications per ESFRI member country
Facilitating economic activities	9. Share of users associated with industry and publications with industry 10. Income from commercial activities and the number of entities paying for service
Outreach to the public	11. Engagement achieved by direct contact 12. Outreach through media 13. Outreach via the RI’s own web and social media
Optimising data use	14. Number of publicly available data sets used externally
Provision of scientific advice	15. Participation by RIs in policy related activities 16. Citations in policy related publications
Facilitating international co-operation	17. Share of users and publications per non-ESFRI member country 18. International trainees 19. Number of members of the RI from non-ESFRI countries
Optimising management	20. Revenues 21. Extent of resources made available

Figure 3: Numerical KPIs per Set Objective (source: Ref. 5)

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

It should be highlighted that careful IPR management is a significant component *en route* to successful exploitation of any innovation capacity. Since significant innovation outcomes of major importance are expected to derive within E-RIHS, major attention is given to the management of IPR issues, linked to researchers and organizations involved. Legal aspects connected to IPRs, on the one hand, and open innovation, on the other hand, are issues that need to be examined across E-RIHS in order to ensure efficient knowledge diffusion without compromising specific rights of individuals (or organizations). Considering the multi-actor nature of E-RIHS (providers, users, support scientists/engineers, etc.) it is important to work towards a well-defined and balanced IP support system, adjustable to the different types of innovations envisaged so as to promote creativity and innovation exploiting the broad knowledge basis in the E-RIHS ecosystem.

⁵ https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/ESFRI_WG_Monitoring_Report.pdf

⁶ IPERION HS Deliverable D1.1 “Quality Monitoring Plan with KPIs”

Importantly, all of the above relate to the existing national and EU legal and administrative framework for granting and protecting IPRs as well as guidelines and initiatives of international organisations. Recommendations of IPR management practice, guidelines on how to deal with sensitive IPR issues, Creative Commons, Open Access Movement, ethical and other issues related with IPR within E-RIHS have been analysed in the E-RIHS PP deliverable D4.4,⁷ while additional work is currently in progress in IPERION HS, WP 6, Task 6.5.

Briefly, a strategy for structuring and implementing an IPR Management Plan (IPRMP) in E-RIHS, taking into consideration the particularities and specificities of the HS sector, involves:

- Assessing and reaching a clear understanding of the portfolio of technological and instrumental assets, newly developed by the partnership, copyrighted works, innovative procedures, confidential information material susceptible to IPR protection, and achieve a comprehensive understanding of their value.
- Evaluating and adopting an IPRMP that is coherent with the distributed nature and the business plan of E-RIHS ERIC and enables the pursuit of its international objectives.
- Developing a dynamical strategy for implementation that foresees future IP developments within the RI in line with the ever-changing HS environment and competitive activities. The strategy should be robust enough to stand periodical reviews, motivate internal IP development and identification and define mechanisms for measuring success regarding IPR protection.

The monitoring mechanisms that need to be introduced by E-RIHS will ensure the timely detection of innovations that need to seek IP protection so as to develop an adequate strategy that will allow further exploitation of those innovations. This is a critical aspect, especially when several actors are involved in the development of an innovation and certain decisions should be made at the very beginning concerning IP rights, ownership and exploitation potentials of the developed IP.

A more comprehensive document on IPR is under preparation in the context of Task 5, WP06.

5. Exploitation Plan. Objectives.

As pointed out in Section 3, examples of innovative findings successfully exploited by E-RIHS partners are disproportionately few in comparison to the rich innovation potential demonstrated by the multitude of research achievements in HS. This suggests that there exist gaps that prevent exploitation and commercialization of innovation. To bridge these gaps a well-defined plan is needed that will offer methods and routes towards efficient exploitation of the E-RIHS innovation potential. Main components of such a plan will include a number of actions as detailed next.

Training of researchers

Of key importance is to ensure researchers have the right support that will facilitate them to take innovation from the research laboratory to the Heritage Marketplace. This is not a straightforward process. Appropriate specialized training, particularly for young researchers, is essential for developing skills and competences that will facilitate them to understand and determine the innovation potential of an idea, a system, a method or a product, search for the right marketplace, identify opportunities and develop a plan for exploitation.

⁷ E-RIHS PP Deliverable D4.4 “IPR management rules”

Central Liaison Office (CLO) for Innovation

In order to effectively monitor the innovation derived from E-RIHS it is essential to set up an internal mechanism that will liaise with local technology transfer offices (TTO) in the participating organizations which are in charge of assessing the innovation produced. It is important to establish ways for exchanging good practices within the E-RIHS ecosystem. Furthermore, certain procedures and methodologies should be introduced for monitoring all steps in the pipeline of innovation. This coordination role is proposed to be undertaken by the Central Liaison Office (CLO).

Facilitating exploitation – Lowering barriers

The Central Liaison Office (CLO) in collaboration with the TTOs of the involved partners (and national or international experts) will provide customized assistance and consultancy services to researchers in cases of exploitable innovation outcomes. An evaluation mechanism will be established by the CLO, to monitor progress, advice on key areas for development, indicate exploitation opportunities and suggest adjustments when things ‘go wrong’. Researcher teams will be encouraged to discuss with TT consultants concerning issues related to IPR management, business development, market analysis and funding opportunities. Through this process the involved parties will have the opportunity to recognize from the early phases the innovation potential of their work in relation to the HS market and decide on the appropriate exploitation routes and the related steps. In addition, the CLO will facilitate and enable contacts of the interested parties with investors and venture capital firms, organizing special “Innovation events” and establishing channels of communication.

Innovation radar

E-RIHS will set up a mechanism to exploit emerging opportunities. The priority assigned to different directions will depend on the evolving challenges but also on the current momentum and related potential (human resources and funding schemes). The radar will be a mechanism/tool that will detect emerging opportunities in terms of financing innovation, collaboration opportunities, funding schemes and encouraging synergies between stakeholders. All E-RIHS partners could contribute to this mechanism (likely in the form of an online repository) where they could submit their information on emerging opportunities so that all E-RIHS partners could have access to it.

It is of importance that the Innovation radar ‘scans’ not only the landscape within the E-RIHS ecosystem but a much broader range (for example, medical diagnostic technologies, automotive and aerospace, construction and buildings sector or forensics and environment) where relevant ideas and technologies grow. This way, it becomes possible to adapt new tools and methods and introduce them to heritage applications and then exploit them in the Heritage marketplace.

Collaboration with Industry

Industry is considered as a key player in the development and the future of RIs, and according to the Innovation Working Group (INNO WG) a “bi-directional” focus is put in all its activities on the improvement of the mutual cooperation between RIs and industry,⁸ placing industry among the three actors for enabling regional development. In the case of HS, such a multi-disciplinary domain with a multi-faceted field of

⁸ The Working Group on Innovation (INNO WG) was set-up in 2013 in order “to propose to the Forum the broad lines of a strategic plan for an industry-oriented cooperation” of the Research Infrastructures (RIs), ESFRI Scripta Volume III, Innovation-oriented cooperation of Research Infrastructures European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures Innovation Working Group, ISBN PDF: 978-88-943243-1-0

applications, “Industry” may be considered with a wider view as anyone outside of pure academia with revenue/ commercial potential. In general, “application field” might be a more appropriate term than “industry” in the common point of view. Considering industry in a broader sense as revenue-driven commercial companies and/or organisations, museums or galleries, private companies of conservators-restorers, can be considered as specific “industries” in the culture heritage field. Obviously, there is a wide spectrum of what could be classed as industry for HS and therefore, large potential for E-RIHS industry users.

6. Concluding remarks

This document outlines aspects of innovation considered relevant for HS and proposes general actions for an Exploitation plan.

Innovation is an essential component of the strategic objectives of E-RIHS. It encompasses novel research actions, offer of unique access services and provision of smart tools. Exploiting innovation, for the benefit of the E-RIHS ecosystem and the society, requires a number of actions along the innovation chain, including the presence of an efficient monitoring and evaluation system, appropriate knowledge and technology transfer channels, proper IPR protection and efficient communication with key stakeholders both in the public and the private sectors. An overall systematic approach to the above will ensure success and sustainability of E-RIHS as an innovator and as a leader in the global HS landscape.

Useful references

Chesbrough, H. (2006), *Open Business Models: How to Thrive in the New Innovation Landscape*. HBS Press. 2006. ISBN 978-1422104279

Curley M., Salmelin B. (2018) Openness to Innovation and Innovation Culture. In: *Open Innovation 2.0. Innovation, Technology, and Knowledge Management*. Springer, Cham., DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-62878-3_13](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-62878-3_13)

Kowalska, M. and Targowski, P., (2019, December 23). Success stories: impact of 15 years of European Research Infrastructure Projects on Heritage Science (Version 2.71). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592059>

E-RIHS PP DOCUMENTS

<http://www.e-rihs.eu/>

- E-RIHS PP Deliverable D6.2 “Sustainability document for business plan”
- E-RIHS PP Deliverable D9.2 “Analysis of the Innovation Background”
- E-RIHS PP Deliverable D9.3 “Innovation Strategy”
- E-RIHS PP Deliverable D9.4 “Innovation Agenda”

EU DOCUMENTS

- The 3 O’s policy - Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World, (2016) ISBN 978-92-79-57346-0, DOI: 10.2777/061652
- G. Sonkoly and T. Vahtikari, *Innovation in Cultural Heritage - For an integrated European Research Policy*, European Union 2018, DOI:10.2777/673069
- Sustainable European Research Infrastructures – A call for action COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT— Long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures, 2017, PDF DOI:10.2777/76269 KI-01-17-790-EN-N
- J. Hrusak, A. Harrison and L. Lenoir (Eds), *ESFRI Scripta Volume II, Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures* ESFRI, Long-Term Sustainability Working Group, 2017, ISBN PDF: 978-88-901562-8-1
- *Radical Innovation: Humanities Research Crossing Knowledge Boundaries and Fostering Deep Change*: D/2015/13.324/12, Science Europe Scientific Committee for the Humanities, 2015

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) DOCUMENTS

<https://www.oecd.org/innovation/>

- OECD (2021), *OECD Science, Technology and Innovation Outlook 2021: Times of Crisis and Opportunity*, OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/75f79015-en>
- OECD (2020), *The Digitalisation of Science, Technology and Innovation: Key Developments and Policies*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b9e4a2c0-en>